

Online Companion - Distributionally Robust Power and Gas Dispatch with Multivariate and Correlated Uncertainty

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This paper serves as an electronic companion to the paper [1]. Sections 1 and 2, respectively introduce mathematical definitions regarding the Wasserstein distance and the CVaR approximation for Distributionally Robust Chance Constraints (DRCCs). The complete final model formulation under ambiguity sets \mathcal{A} , and $\mathcal{A}^{\text{Bench}}$ are given in Sections 3 and 4. The real-time stage optimization problem is given in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 provides the economical and technical network parameters for the real-life Belgian power and gas systems.

1 The Wasserstein distance

The distance between two distributions, namely \mathbb{Q} and $\hat{\mathbb{Q}}_N$, may be assessed via the Wasserstein probability metric [2], whose mathematical formulation is given by

$$d_W(\mathbb{Q}, \hat{\mathbb{Q}}_N) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min_{\Pi} \int_{\Xi^2} \|\tilde{\xi} - \hat{\xi}_N\| \Pi(d\tilde{\xi}, d\hat{\xi}_N) \\ \text{s.t.} \\ \Pi \text{ is a joint distribution of } \tilde{\xi} \text{ and } \hat{\xi}_N \\ \text{with marginals } \mathbb{Q} \text{ and } \hat{\mathbb{Q}}_N, \text{ respectively} \end{array} \right\}. \quad (1)$$

Problem (1) refers to a transportation problem that displaces the samples from $\hat{\mathbb{Q}}_N$ to \mathbb{Q} , in the cheapest way with regards to the transportation cost $\|\tilde{\xi} - \hat{\xi}_N\|$. The Wasserstein distance corresponds therefore to the optimal transportation cost which is achieved by the optimal transportation plan Π .

2 CVaR Approximation of DRCCs

In this section, we focus on a generic DRCC of the type

$$\min_{\mathbb{Q} \in \mathcal{A}} \mathbb{Q} \left(a^\top \xi + b \leq 0 \right) \geq 1 - \epsilon \quad (2)$$

where $a \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{K}|}$ and $b \in \mathbb{R}$. We provide the required reformulations for both \mathcal{A} and $\mathcal{A}^{\text{Bench}}$ that can be applied to each constraint in the overall set of DRCCs of the original dispatch problem. As thoroughly discussed in [3]-[4], a generic DRCC may be conservatively approximated by a CVaR constraint, as suggested by the following implication

$$\max_{\mathbb{Q} \in \mathcal{A}} \mathbb{Q}\text{-CVaR}_\epsilon(a^\top \xi + b) \leq 0 \Rightarrow \min_{\mathbb{Q} \in \mathcal{A}} \mathbb{Q} \left(a^\top \xi + b \leq 0 \right) \geq 1 - \epsilon. \quad (3)$$

The approximation is conservative because CVaR inherently accounts for the severity (i.e., amplitude) of the constraint violation, which has the effect of reducing the constraint violation probability pursued by the decision maker. By definition, the CVaR constraint can be recast as

$$\max_{\mathbb{Q} \in \mathcal{A}} \mathbb{Q}\text{-CVaR}_\epsilon(a^\top \xi + b) = \min_{\tau \in \mathbb{R}} \tau + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \max_{\mathbb{Q} \in \mathcal{A}} \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}} \left[[a^\top \xi + b - \tau]^+ \right] \quad (4)$$

where $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$ represents an auxiliary variable and the operator $[\cdot]^+ = \max(\cdot, 0)$. Using this technique to model the DRCCs yields worst-case expectation problems in the constraints, that can be reformulated using

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\mathbb{Q} \in \mathcal{A}} \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}} [a^\top \xi + b] = & \quad (5a) \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min_{\lambda, \sigma_i, \Lambda \succeq 0, \zeta_i} \lambda \rho + \langle \Lambda, \Sigma \rangle_{\text{F}} + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_i \\ \text{s.t. } \mathcal{F}_i \succeq 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|\zeta_i\|_* \leq \lambda \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \end{array} \right\} \text{ with } \mathcal{F}_i = & \begin{bmatrix} \Lambda & -\frac{1}{2}a + \frac{1}{2}\zeta_i - \Lambda\mu_0 \\ (-\frac{1}{2}a + \frac{1}{2}\zeta_i - \Lambda\mu_0)^\top & \sigma_i - \zeta_i^\top \hat{\xi}_i \\ & -b + \mu_0^\top \Lambda \mu_0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5b) \end{aligned}$$

for the ambiguity set \mathcal{A} , where $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}, \Lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{K}| \times |\mathcal{K}|}, \sigma_i \in \mathbb{R}, \zeta_i \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{K}|}$ and $\mu_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{K}|}$. Regarding ambiguity set $\mathcal{A}^{\text{Bench}}$, the reformulation of the worst-case expectation problem is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\mathbb{Q} \in \mathcal{A}^{\text{Bench}}} \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}} [a^\top \xi + b] = & \quad (6a) \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min_{\lambda, \sigma_i, \gamma_i} \lambda \rho + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_i \\ \text{s.t. } a^\top \hat{\xi}_i + b + \gamma_i^\top (d - C\xi) \leq \sigma_i \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|C^\top \gamma_i - a\|_* \leq \lambda \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \end{array} \right\} & \quad (6b) \end{aligned}$$

where $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}, \sigma_i \in \mathbb{R}, \gamma_i \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{K}|}$ and $C\xi \leq d$ defines a support of uncertainty, with $C \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{K}| \times |\mathcal{K}|}$.

3 Model reformulation under ambiguity set \mathcal{A}

In this section, we provide the key steps for reformulating the distributionally robust day-ahead joint power and gas dispatch problem under the ambiguity set \mathcal{A} . Distributionally robust optimization appears in *i*) the objective function, and *ii*) the DRCCs. Regarding the objective function, the reformulation is provided in the parent paper [1]. Regarding the DRCCs, we provide an example of reformulation for the inequality (1d) in the parent paper:

$$\min_{\mathbb{Q} \in \mathcal{A}} \mathbb{Q} \left(\overline{p_{e,t}} + Y_{e,t} \tilde{\xi}_t \leq p_e^{\max} \right) \geq 1 - \bar{\epsilon}_{e,t} \quad \forall e \in \mathcal{E} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (7)$$

By applying the aforementioned CVaR reformulation with ambiguity set \mathcal{A} , the following set of equations conservatively approximates (7)

$$\bar{\tau}_{e,t} + \frac{1}{\bar{\epsilon}_{e,t}} \left(\bar{\lambda}_{e,t} \rho + \langle \bar{\Lambda}_{e,t}, \Sigma \rangle_{\text{F}} + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \bar{y}_{e,t,i} \right) \leq 0 \quad \forall e \in \mathcal{E} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (8)$$

$$\left[\begin{array}{cc} \bar{\Lambda}_{e,t} & -\frac{1}{2}Y_{e,t} + \frac{1}{2}\bar{\zeta}_{e,t,i,1} \\ (-\frac{1}{2}Y_{e,t} + \frac{1}{2}\bar{\zeta}_{e,t,i,1})^\top & \bar{\tau}_{e,t} + p_e^{\max} - \bar{p}_{e,t} - \bar{\zeta}_{e,t,i,1}^\top \hat{\xi}_i + \bar{y}_{e,t,i} \end{array} \right] \succeq 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad \forall e \in \mathcal{E} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (9)$$

$$\left[\begin{array}{cc} \bar{\Lambda}_{e,t} & \frac{1}{2}\bar{\zeta}_{e,t,i,2} \\ (\frac{1}{2}\bar{\zeta}_{e,t,i,2})^\top & -\bar{\zeta}_{e,t,i,2}^\top \hat{\xi}_i + \bar{y}_{e,t,i} \end{array} \right] \succeq 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad \forall e \in \mathcal{E} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (10)$$

$$\|\bar{\zeta}_{e,t,i,j}\|_* \leq \bar{\lambda}_{e,t} \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J} \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad \forall e \in \mathcal{E} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (11)$$

For the sake of clarity, we omit the complete formulation of the resulting problem, which is obtained by applying the same technique to DRCCs (1c) to (1m).

4 Model reformulation under ambiguity set $\mathcal{A}^{\text{Bench}}$

In this section, we provide the key steps for reformulating the distributionally robust day-ahead joint power and gas dispatch problem under the ambiguity set \mathcal{A} . First, the objective function reformulates as follows:

$$\min_{\Theta} \sum_{t=1}^{|\mathcal{T}|} \left(\sum_{e=1}^{|\mathcal{E}|} c_e \bar{p}_{e,t} + \sum_{g=1}^{|\mathcal{G}|} c_g \bar{p}_{g,t} \right) + \max_{\mathbb{Q} \in \mathcal{A}^{\text{Bench}}} \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}} \left[\sum_{t=1}^{|\mathcal{T}|} \left(\sum_{e=1}^{|\mathcal{E}|} c_e Y_{e,t}^{\top} \tilde{\xi}_t + \sum_{g=1}^{|\mathcal{G}|} c_g V_{g,t}^{\top} \tilde{\xi}_t \right) \right] = \quad (12a)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min_{\lambda, \sigma_i, \gamma_i} \sum_{t=1}^{|\mathcal{T}|} \lambda_t \rho + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_{i,t} \\ \text{s.t.} \sum_{e=1}^{|\mathcal{E}|} c_e Y_{e,t}^{\top} \tilde{\xi}_t + \sum_{g=1}^{|\mathcal{G}|} c_g V_{g,t}^{\top} \tilde{\xi}_t + \gamma_{i,t}^{\top} (d - C \tilde{\xi}_t) \leq \sigma_{i,t} \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \\ \|C^{\top} \gamma_{i,t} - \sum_{e=1}^{|\mathcal{E}|} c_e Y_{e,t} - \sum_{g=1}^{|\mathcal{G}|} c_g V_{g,t}\|_* \leq \lambda \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \end{array} \right\} \quad (12b)$$

Regarding the DRCCs, we provide an example of reformulation for the inequality (1d) in the parent paper:

$$\min_{\mathbb{Q} \in \mathcal{A}} \mathbb{Q} \left(\bar{p}_{e,t} + Y_{e,t} \tilde{\xi}_t \leq p_e^{\max} \right) \geq 1 - \bar{\epsilon}_{e,t} \quad \forall e \in \mathcal{E} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (13)$$

By applying the aforementioned CVaR reformulation with ambiguity set $\mathcal{A}^{\text{Bench}}$, the following set of equations conservatively approximates (13)

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \bar{\tau}_{e,t} + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(\bar{\lambda}_{e,t} \rho + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \bar{\sigma}_{e,t,i} \right) \leq 0 \\ \bar{p}_{e,t} + Y_{e,t} \tilde{\xi}_t - p_e^{\max} - \bar{\tau}_{e,t} + \bar{\gamma}_{e,t,i,1}^{\top} (d - C \hat{\xi}_{i,t}) \leq \bar{\sigma}_{e,t,i} \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{e,t,i,2}^{\top} (d - C \hat{\xi}_{i,t}) \leq \bar{\sigma}_{e,t,i} \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|C^{\top} \bar{\gamma}_{e,t,i,1} - Y_{e,t}\|_* \leq \bar{\lambda}_{e,t} \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|C^{\top} \bar{\gamma}_{e,t,i,2}\|_* \leq \bar{\lambda}_{e,t} \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{e,t,i,1} \geq 0; \bar{\gamma}_{e,t,i,2} \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \end{array} \right\} \quad \forall e \in \mathcal{E} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (14)$$

For the sake of clarity, we omit the complete formulation of the resulting problem, which is obtained by applying the same technique to DRCCs (1c) to (1m).

5 Real-time stage program

This section presents the real-time stage optimization problem (15) that is used to assess the ex-post performance of the different sets of decisions.

$$Y_{e,t}, V_{g,t}, \Delta d_t^e, \Delta d_t^g, \Delta w_t \sum_{t=1}^{|\mathcal{T}|} \left(\sum_{e=1}^{|\mathcal{E}|} c_e Y_{e,t}^\top \hat{\xi}_{j,t} + \sum_{g=1}^{|\mathcal{G}|} c_g V_{g,t}^\top \hat{\xi}_{j,t} + V_{\text{Shed}}^e \Delta d_t^e + V_{\text{Shed}}^g \Delta d_t^g \right) \quad (15a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } 0 \leq \Delta d_t^e \leq \overline{D^{e,\text{res}}} + \overline{D^{e,\text{ind}}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (15b)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta d_t^g \leq \overline{D^{g,\text{res}}} + \overline{D^{g,\text{ind}}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (15c)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta w_t \leq \overline{\Omega}_t \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (15d)$$

$$p_{e,t}^{\min} \leq \overline{p_{e,t}} + Y_{e,t}^\top \hat{\xi}_{j,t} \leq p_{e,t}^{\max} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (15e)$$

$$p_{g,t}^{\min} \leq \overline{p_{g,t}} + V_{g,t}^\top \hat{\xi}_{j,t} \leq p_{g,t}^{\max} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (15f)$$

$$\sum_{e=1}^{|\mathcal{E}|} Y_{e,t} \hat{\xi}_{j,t} + \Delta d_t^e - \Delta w = \hat{\xi}_{1,j,t} + \hat{\xi}_{2,j,t} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (15g)$$

$$\sum_{g=1}^{|\mathcal{G}|} V_{g,t} \hat{\xi}_{j,t} + \Delta d_t^g = \hat{\xi}_{3,j,t} + \hat{\xi}_{4,j,t} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (15h)$$

The objective function (15a) models the real-time operational costs incurred by the energy activation costs and the value of (power and gas) demand shedding V_{Shed}^e and V_{Shed}^g (the wind spillage cost is assumed to be equal to zero). Equations (15b) and (15c) imposes physical limitations on power and gas demand shedding Δd_t^e and Δd_t^g while equation (15d) limits the wind power spillage Δw_t . The actual recourse actions $Y_{e,t} \hat{\xi}_{j,t}$ and $V_{g,t} \hat{\xi}_{j,t}$ are limited by the capacity bound $p_{e,t}^{\min}$, $p_{e,t}^{\max}$, $p_{g,t}^{\min}$, and $p_{g,t}^{\max}$ in (15e) and (15f) determined in day-ahead. The real-time power and gas balances are ensured respectively by (15g) and (15h).

6 Network Parameters

As our case study, we use the real-life Belgian power and gas systems which topologies are represented in Fig. 1. The economical and technical data are collected in Tables 1 and 2.

(a) Belgian electrical grid topology (plain lines are 380 kV and dashed lines are 220 kV).

(b) Belgian gas grid topology.

Fig. 1: The real-life Belgian power and gas systems.

The power system data is given by Table 1. It includes electricity generating units parameters such as location node, marginal production cost c_e in €/MWh, minimum and maximum

capacity p_e^{\min} and p_e^{\max} in MW.

Wind farms are also connected to the power system. Their maximum capacity is aggregated for each province and then equally distributed on the nodes pertaining to a given province (11 provinces in total). The twelfth wind farm corresponds to the offshore wind and is connected to “Eeklo noord” node. The corresponding maximum wind farm capacity $W_{(w,w)}$ in MW is also given in Table 1.

The electricity demands comprise residential and industrial compounds. Their respective location node, electrical sharing (among the nodes) in % and value of curtailed load V_{Shed} in €/MWh are referred in Table 1. The lines are characterized by the nodes they connect, their per-unit reactance as well as their maximum line capacity in MW.

Besides, the gas transmission system connects gas wells, gas demands as well as gas-fired power plants via the pipelines. In particular, the gas wells are characterized by their connecting node, marginal production cost, and minimum and maximum output debit.

The residential and industrial gas demands are distributed among their related nodes. Border exchanges happen with France, Netherlands, and Luxembourg, and are allocated to the nodes of the gas system given in Table 2. The transit is also specified and is fixed.

Finally, the pipelines are characterized by their connecting nodes, Weymouth constant $K_{m,u}$ in $(\text{MNm}^3/(\text{bar}\cdot\text{h}))^2$ and linepack constant $S_{m,u}$ in MNm^3/bar .

Note that the minimum and maximum pressures PR^{\min} and PR^{\max} are 40 and 85 bars. The gas compression factor Γ is equal for all compressors and is given by 1.5. The conversion factor $\varphi_e = 5 \cdot 10^{-5}$.

Table 1: Technical data for electricity generating units, wind power generating units, electricity demands and transmission lines

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
Electricity generating units														
Location [node]	29	42	24	10	11	1	36	35	17	9	37	38	39	40
Marginal production cost c_e [€/MWh]	12.8	12.8	12.8	12.8	12.8	12.8	12.8	12.8	12.8	12.8	9.5	10	10	12.8
Capacity $P_{e,max}$ [MW]	188	663	451	513	465	350	384	405	422	3000	1000	1000	1000	86
Minimum output power $P_{e,min}$ [MW]	52.64	185.64	126.28	143.64	130.2	98.0	107.52	113.4	118.16	840.0	280.0	280.0	280.0	24.08
Wind power generating units														
Location [node]	3, 11, 31	9, 14, 18, 42	8, 35, 43	15, 16, 17, 36	13, 41	6, 32	4, 10	19	5, 12, 20, 21, 24, 26, 28, 29, 33, 37, 38, 39, 40, 46	1, 7	2, 22, 23, 25, 27, 30, 44, 45	11	1, 7	2, 22, 23, 25, 27, 30, 44, 45
Installed capacity [MW]	133.3	114.9	113.4	169.4	109.4	85.4	101.7	5.3	240.3	48.3	102.7	15	16	17
Electricity demands														
Location [node]	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
Electrical sharing [%]	2.73	3.7	5.39	4.82	2.68	0.0	0.0	2.68	2.41	2.41	0.0	0.0	4.82	2.41
Curtaillment cost [€/MWh]	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000
Electricity demands														
Location [node]	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
Electrical sharing [%]	5.39	2.87	0.48	0.32	2.47	0.0	0.0	0.46	5.68	0.68	0.0	5.09	0.0	0.0
Curtaillment cost [€/MWh]	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000
Electricity demands														
Location [node]	35	36	37	38	38	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46
Electrical sharing [%]	2.97	0.0	0.0	4.82	0.0	2.41	3.38	0.0	0.94	1.34	1.34	44	45	46
Curtaillment cost [€/MWh]	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000
Transmission lines: From node														
To node	1	2	3	3	3	4	4	4	5	5	5	6	6	6
Reactance [per-unit]	0.121	0.313	0.075	0.130	0.051	0.053	0.155	0.046	0.007	0.007	0.145	0.145	0.051	0.050
Capacity [MW]	1184.7	1295.1	1295.1	1184.4	1295.1	1295.1	1295.1	1184.4	1184.4	1184.4	1373.4	1184.4	1295.1	1184.4
Transmission lines: From node														
To node	6	7	7	8	8	8	9	9	9	10	11	12	12	12
Reactance [per-unit]	0.069	0.145	0.106	0.006	0.110	0.041	0.075	0.068	0.075	0.024	0.226	0.034	0.039	0.185
Capacity [MW]	1373.4	1295.1	1295.1	1184.4	1184.4	1184.4	1295.1	1295.1	1184.4	1184.4	1295.1	1295.1	1295.1	1184.4
Transmission lines: From node														
To node	12	12	12	13	13	14	15	15	16	16	17	18	19	2
Reactance [per-unit]	0.010	0.010	0.009	0.011	0.034	0.139	0.046	0.046	0.069	0.107	0.115	0.189	0.112	0.062
Capacity [MW]	1184.4	1184.4	1295.1	1295.1	1184.4	1295.1	1296.9	1295.1	1295.1	1295.1	1295.1	1295.1	1184.4	305.1
Transmission lines: From node														
To node	2	20	20	21	21	5	22	23	24	24	25	26	27	29, 30
Reactance [per-unit]	0.084	0.142	0.026	0.031	0.033	0.010	0.097	0.075	0.089	0.022	0.022	0.053	0.113	0.058, 0.021
Capacity [MW]	305.1	364.5	374.4	334.8	610.2	480.6	426.6	426.6	374.4	270.0	305.1	334.8	364.5	355.5, 364.5

Table 2: Technical data for gas wells, gas demands and pipelines

Gas wells		1	2	3	4	5	6
Location [node]		1	5	9	17	18	21
Production cost [€/MNm ³]		2000	3000	4000	5000	6000	7000
Maximum debit [MNm ³ /h]		5	1	0.5	2.2	1.5	1
Minimum debit [MNm ³ /h]		0	0	0	0	0	0
Residential demands							
Location [node]		1	2	3	4	5	6
Demand forecast ¹ [MNm ³]		2	6	8	9	11	13
		0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Industrial demands							
Location [node]		1	2	3	4	5	6
Demand forecast ² [MNm ³]		12	13	14	15	19	23
		0.0026	0.0026	0.0026	0.0026	0.0026	0.0026
Border exchanges							
Location [node]		25	5	21	2	3	4
Neighbouring country		France	Netherlands	Netherlands	Netherlands	Luxembourg	Luxembourg
Transit quantity ³ [MNm ³]		0.46	-0.48	-0.48	-0.48	-0.48	-0.002
Pipelines: From node							
To node		11	12	13	18	20	20
$K_{m,u}$ [(MNm ³ /(bar.h)) ²]		0.144	0.0827	0.00312	0.00026	0.000936	0.000347
$S_{m,u}$ [MNm ³ /bar]		0.168	0.0349	0.00106	0.0127	0.00353	0.00952
Pipelines: From node							
To node		23	23	26	27	2	5
$K_{m,u}$ [(MNm ³ /(bar.h)) ²]		0.0000641	0.000841	0.0512	0.101	0.00601	0.00739
$S_{m,u}$ [MNm ³ /bar]		0.0515	0.0722	0.0143	0.0309	0.0215	0.0142

¹ The total residential demand forecast equals 0.45 MNm³ and is distributed uniformly among nodes with residential demands.

² The total industrial demand forecast equals 0.036 MNm³ and is distributed uniformly among nodes with industrial demands.

³ Negative quantities indicate an import of gas.

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